

**AFRICAN CULTURAL IDENTITY IN CHIGOZIE OBIOMA'S
*AN ORCHESTRA OF MINORITIES***

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ABSTRACT

This research work discusses African cultural identity in Chigozie Obioma's *An Orchestra of Minorities*. The study is aimed at exploring and examining the Igbo worldview in the novel and analyzing how these perspectives shape the narratives and characters within the literary work. Sociological criticism is the theoretical framework of the study. The research employs a qualitative approach, utilizing textual analysis and literary criticism to identify and interpret the cultural elements embedded in the novels. The findings of this study reveal several commonalities and divergences in the portrayal of the Igbo worldview across the novel. Obioma illuminates the centrality of ancestral heritage, communal values, and oral tradition in the Igbo society in *An Orchestra of Minorities*. The novel offers a comprehensive exploration of the dynamic interplay between tradition and modernity, shedding light on the Igbo cultural heritage and its continued relevance in the 21st century.

Keywords: Nigerian novel, African novel, Igbo worldview, Cultural identity.

Introduction

It is an axiomatic fact that literature mirrors human lives and experiences in the society. This study seeks to demonstrate that the Igbo people have a rich cultural heritage and way of life peculiar to them, which is amply demonstrated in Chigozie Obioma's novel, *An Orchestra of Minorities*. It may not be mere exaggeration to say that the Igbo people have an intensely rich cultural heritage. From their

marriage to way of recreation, from the articulation of proverbial lore to their construction of myth, folktales, and folkways, and even their way of greeting, the Igbo people are distinctly marked for their peculiarity in cultural manifestations. Several scholars, both indigenous and foreign, have given primacy to this subject, yet this seeming cultural cauldron promises to integrate an inexhaustible repository of resources from whence new perspectives on the Igbo worldview can be extrapolated.

The Igbo people are considered to be one of the three major ethnic groups in Nigeria. With high population density in the Southeastern part of Nigeria, the Igbo people are distinct in terms of their origin, history, commerce, government, language and culture. Regardless of the different states they occupy in Nigeria and the different sub-ethnic groups that are identified within the Igbo citizenry, they are largely characterized by a monolithic construction of worldview. Predominantly, it is the construction of this worldview that, arguably, determines the portraiture of several aspects of the Igbo people lives. In his critical essay entitled *Perspectives on Aspects of Culture in Nigeria*, Nnadube Ejiogu (1) posits that “it is a common knowledge that the worldview of a particular group goes to determine the behavioural pattern of that group.” He further adds that “worldview suggests how people perceive and explain their world” (1). Chinwe Nwoye (306) submits that “worldview refers to the explanations that inform people's knowledge on certain phenomena or changes in their environment.” Similarly, Alexander Animalu (43) in his lecture titled *A Way of Life in Modern Scientific Age* adumbrates that “worldviews refer to a people's way of organising their activities which explain the how and why of daily existence.” If these clarifications on the concept of worldview are anything to go by, it then stands to reason that in order to fully understand the Igbo people and what motivates their way of life, it is, indeed, apt to understand their worldview. Ejiogu (1) rightly remarks that “one would be committing an error to prejudge the culture of a group of people by the standards of a different culture/group especially because of the variance in their worldviews.” In this regard, literature mediates as an agency through which one can gain fraternal invitation into the worldview of the Igbo people. It is undeniable that the self-concept of a group of people like the Igbos is largely influenced by their worldview which Isiodore Okpewho in *Myth in Africa: A Study of its Aesthetic and Cultural Relevance* refers to as “the irreducible aesthetic substratum in all varieties of human cultural endeavor, from one generation to another” (69).

The current reality in its exactitude ostensibly confirms that modernity has engendered a hybrid sense of cultural belonging, so that, the emerging generation of Igbo populace, especially those in the city are beginning to lose their sense of identity. The need for the continuous defending and preserving of the Igbo cultural heritage through chronicling critical aspects of her worldview is highly essential. It

is important to state that the identity of a people are symbiotically connected with the philosophy they identify with, therefore, when there is an erosion of such identity, then the people loses their essence. As a consequence, the Igbo people must find a way to preserve their philosophy and that which gives them their identity even in the face of a rapidly changing society. Furthermore, there have been paucity of studies on Igbo worldview in Chigozie Obioma's *An Orchestra of Minorities*. This study is an enterprise at filling this gap in literary scholarship. The following research questions shall be answered in the study: What are the cultural manifestations peculiar to the Igbo people? How did the Igbo people preserve their worldview? What are the various instances of Igbo worldview demonstrated in Chigozie Obioma's *An Orchestra of Minorities*?

Theoretical Framework

In order to appreciate this discourse and appropriately respond to the objectives of this research, it is pertinent to admit that traditional theories and the structuralist/post structuralist theories may not be able to do holistic justice. Thus, the theory that assumes a convenient balance here is 'sociological criticism' or the 'sociology of literature' or 'social criticism' According to Adams Hazard (198), sociological criticism is Literary criticism directed to understanding (or placing) literature in its larger social context; it codifies the literary strategies that are employed to represent social constructs through a sociological methodology.

Sociological criticism analyzes both how the social functions in literature and how literature works in society. This form of literary criticism was introduced by Kenneth Burke (1971), a 20th century literary and critical theorist, whose article, "Literature As Equipment for Living" outlines the specification and significance of such a critique.

This theoretical approach attempts to appreciate literary works from the context of culture, economy, and politics. Its primary concern is to analyse a literary work in the light of the society it emanates from. It has been offered that literature does not operate in vacuum, it is usually conditioned by the society it aims to mirror. It is this duty that places literature at its cross-current exchange with sociology. Therefore, this approach explores the relationship between the creative product and the society. Also worth noting is that sociological criticism is equally interested in both the author and the content of his creative production. It (the criticism) seeks to fashion the equilibrium that exist between literary texts and the author's society. It critically examines the author's connection to their society and their position in that society. Equally important is that the sociological approach can mediate over exploring retrospect of the very past, reminiscence of the immediate past, and what is obtainable in the existential present in order to accurately predict the prospective future. In all, the social interpretation of literary texts is of huge benefit to the

society as it places before it, a metaphorical mirror, with the aim of illuminating, with which it can properly evaluate and reorder itself at the point of societal self-discovery.

Previous Studies on *An Orchestra of Minorities*

Undoubtedly, there is a mass body of works on Obioma's *An Orchestra of Minorities* that detail the Igbo worldview. The analyses contained in a number of these literature validate the notion that the Igbos are not just a distinct group of people within Sub-Saharan Africa, but they also possess their equally distinct way of life which takes its root in the philosophy and worldview of the people. Obioma's text may not be able to boast of such a reception. However, substantial materials on the work lucidly capture discourses relevant to the research inquest here.

Critics have likewise examined the notion of the Igbo worldview in Obioma's fiction, *An Orchestra of Minorities*. Paul Eaton's review of the novel captures some of the main foci of the text. Eaton is able to collapse these foci in the expression he uses in describing the book. Eaton (1) notes that the text is "as a cross between epic, tragedy, cosmology, and mythology". This significantly follows that it is an impossible task to divorce the text from its authorial essence of projecting the worldview of the Igbo people. As the critic compares Obioma's text to classical examples such as *The Odyssey*, *The Illiad*, *Seven Famous Greek Plays*, *Agamemnon*, *Antigone*, and *The Frogs*, he defends that Obioma's text does not just elevate the philosophical nuance that is equally seen in the works but also preserves the Igbo philosophical values.

Sameer Thomas also carries out a book review of the text. The opening gambit of Thomas's rendition reads, "*An Orchestra of Minorities* by Chigozie Obioma is a novel that blends Igbo cosmology with penetrating emotional and psychological realism in order to present to its reader a tragedy that is at once classical and contemporary" (197). He further adds that "the form of the novel is particularly interesting, being entirely narrated by Chinonso's Chi [...] explain[ing] his actions to Chukwu, the supreme deity in Igbo cosmology" (197), then goes on to note that "by thus bridging Igbo tradition and contemporary realism, Obioma arguably presents a hybrid of two most recognizable examples of Nigerian fiction in English -- the traditionally rooted *Things Fall Apart* [...] and the [...] contemporary postcolonial ethos of the writing of Chimamanda Ngozi Adichie (197). These submissions expressly confirm that not only is Obioma resolute in projecting the Igbo worldview from the paradigms of Igbo cosmology and myth but that this brave resolution, for Thomas, provides it with the impetus to situate cultural correlation to Achebe's *Things Fall Apart*.

Shireen Quadri (2020) also conducts a review of Obioma's text. His review reiterates what critics have said about the text. However, Quadri plunges deep into giving more vivid illustrations of the areas that demonstrate the Igbo worldview in the text. The critic starts by noting that the *New York Times* describes Obioma as the heir to Chinua Achebe as a result of the text under study. Then goes on to quote Obioma's admission about the text during an interview session conducted:

From the above, it is clearly stated that the authorial vision of the text is, in fact, to, among other things, reveal the beauty and sublimity of the Igbo worldview. Obioma, by his admission, is particular about projecting the philosophical ideology as well as spiritual cadence that sustains the existential reality of the people and their identity in their cosmological order.

Synopsis of Chigozie Obioma's *An Orchestra of Minorities*.

The novel is set on the outskirts of Umuahia, Nigeria and narrated by *chi*, or guardian spirit. *An Orchestra of Minorities* tells the story of Chinonso Solomon Olisa, a poultry farmer in Umuahia. One evening, while driving his van across a bridge over the Imo River, he observes a distraught young woman who attempts to jump from a high-way bridge into the river. Chinonso, horrified by her recklessness, joins her on the roadside and throws two of his prized chickens into the water below to demonstrate the gravity of such a fall. He runs into her again a few weeks later by chance and introduces himself. Ndali is her name, and she is studying to become a pharmacist. Chinonso begins courting Ndali, and the two fall in love, prompting Chinonso to propose marriage and Ndali agrees. Ndali's wealthy family, however, objects to their relationship because of Chinonso's social standing. Chinonso decides to pursue a university education in order to improve his prospects and is accepted into Cyprus International University with the assistance of a friend named Jamike. Chinonso sells his farm to pay the fees, only to discover that Jamike has vanished, leaving him without funds. Despite this setback, Chinonso befriends another Nigerian student named Tobe and reports the theft to Cyprus police together.

Chinonso meets Fiona, a German nurse living in Cyprus, while waiting for Jamike's return. At her house, they have a flirtatious encounter, but when Fiona's husband Ahmed arrives and becomes violent, Chinonso defends her. Fiona, on the other hand, accuses Chinonso of rape, which leads to his arrest and a racially biased trial. He is convicted and sentenced to four years in prison, where he endures abuse and hardship. Chinonso returns to Nigeria filled with rage and seeks vengeance after his conviction is overturned. He unexpectedly encounters Jamike along the way, but instead of exacting his revenge, Chinonso is disarmed by Jamike's genuine remorse. Jamike pays back the stolen money and promises to help Chinonso. Chinonso returns home to discover that Ndali has married another man and has a

son. He quickly realizes that the child is his. Chinonso comes to terms with his circumstances and the consequences of his actions at the end of the story, finding some measure of forgiveness and reconciliation.

In the aftermath of his return and learning of Ndali's marriage and child, Chinonso begs Ndali to keep her promise to him. Ndali is aware that Chinonso was wrongfully convicted, but she has chosen to move on with her life. Chinonso's sanity begins to unravel after yet another disappointment. Chinonso, in a state of insanity, sets fire to Ndali's house, mistaking it for unoccupied. Ndali tragically perishes in the fire, adding to the profound sense of loss and devastation.

African Cultural Identity in *An Orchestra of Minorities*

Chigozie Obioma vividly documents the Igbo understanding of their cosmology in *An Orchestra of Minorities*. Beyond the material or the physical components of the world, it must be acknowledged that other components, even the spiritual, are blended into a whole composite which define or influences the Igbo perspective of life. Because the Igbo cosmological philosophy holds that life is originally structured to accommodate different existential habitations, it becomes normative for such understanding to determine their shared experiential interaction with inhabitants (imagined or material) of the other climes. In an imaginative compositional attempt. Obioma explains that the Igbo cosmology points out that there are three broad concentrations of domains of three spiritual creatures, viz, the domain of God and the ancestors known as Eluigwe, the domain of evil spirits the spirits of the condemned, ghosts and other vagrant spirits known as Benmwo, and the domain of man, animals, plants, forests, land and other elements such as light, sky, water among others, known as Uwa. According to the philosophical orientation that emanates from this ensconcing, only the Uwa is understood to be physical while every other domain is beyond the reach of the physical, yet there is a firm suggestion that the intricate interdependence characterizing these outlooks cannot be wished away. This interaction is even more consolidated by the belief in the principle of reincarnation and the existence of *chi* (guardian spirit). From the commencement of the story to its conclusion, the guardian spirit character, a supposed spiritual entity, is giving prominence. In fact, it is through this spiritual character do we come to fully appreciate the narrative as the spirit renders it. Through this technique, Obioma lucidly registers that congenial to the Igbo worldview, is their unmistakable belief in the spiritual existence.

The account of the *chi* of Chinonso Solomon Olisa makes the metaphysical more tangible and shows how things can flow between different realms through familiar gateways. Even though Obioma maintains the autonomy and independence of these domains, he seems to suggest that the physical and spiritual domains are simultaneously cohabiting and characteristically divided. For example, Obioma

engages the myth of the market to emphasize the exactitude of this cohabitation. It must be registered in tolerable haste that according to the Igbo worldview, the market is not only symbolic (Uzukwu 1982) but has been defined as such because it attempts to reflect how life is understood by the Igbos. Uzukwu in “Igbo World and Ultimate Reality and Meaning” provides a hint on this when he dictates that “the world is a marketplace— and the bargaining characteristics of the marketplace has given a contractual overtone to relations with most spirits” (207). In this essence, what can be inferred from Uzukwu’s dictation is the fact that the Igbo worldview recognizes the myth of the market and the strong belief that the market is not only the place of the activities of humans but also of spirit. Obioma expounds on this as he suggests that it is a portal, a physical and spiritual construction that provide a dwelling arena for commercial interaction for humans and spirits independently. It is the belief, according to the Igbo worldview, that such is the case with life itself which is metonymic of such characteristics.

In *An Orchestra of Minorities*, Obioma relates that the worldview of NdiIgbo does not only recognize frolicking spirit but also recognize a special kind of spirit known as *chi*. The *chi*, following Obioma's observations may be the most important spirit directly designated to man. In fact, as Obioma relates the worldview of his people, the *chi* bears record of its most activities and testified when the need arises to Chukwu. Obioma implies that it is the spirit that goes to the presence of Chukwu and not the physical being to testify to the hosts activity while alive or as he/she is still alive. It must be made prominent that the belief in this seeming abstraction derives from the fact that it is coterminous with the Ndi Igbo understanding that man himself is a spirit being. Whenever such a remark is made the referential signification is usually the Chi (Nwoye,2011).

Apart from the role of Chi, which is evidently spelt out throughout the textual narrative, Obioma uses the character of Chi to reflect the relationship between the physical and spiritual world. The novelist demonstrates his in-depth knowledge of the worldview of the people as he suggests, drawing from the textual evidence, that the Chi is a mobile element that traverses both the corporal and incorporeal world yet remains at the spiritual realm. It is to this Ikechukwu Anthony Kanu delivers that:

The operation of relations within the Igbo African world within the context of Chi, points to the reality that relationship in the Igbo World is both with and between the corporal worlds. It is this connection of chi with relationships within the Igbo World that makes it a fundamental element in the understanding of the dynamics of inter-subjectivity, complementarity, and solidarity [``] chi is the foundation or basis for the interaction or relationship in the Igbo African universe (22).

Obioma interprets Kanu's assertion concerning the guardian spirit quite well in that, it is seen how the spirit element stand before Chukwu to render the account of its host, an obligation only spirit reserves the power to do. Again, within the narrative, it is seen how the guardian spirit is able to repel spiritual attack targeted against its host. Yet, it is noticed how it also attempt to influence something in the physical realm by flashing images in the host's mind which has the potency to inform the decision of the host. In other words, it can be argued that given this negotiation of realms evident in the operation of Chi, the relationship between both worlds is concretized. It is also important to bring to the fore the role and limitations of Chi as constructed in the world view of the Igbos critic have affirmed that not only is Chi a reality but it's role is indisputably established vis-a-vis it's limitations and power of influence. Kanu unequivocally quips that "Chi" [...] occupies an important place in the understanding of the Igbo-speaking African people" (21). He adds that "It remains one of those elements that the Igbo employ to explain or picture the world around them" (21-2). Needless to say, that given the primacy of this element in the construct of the worldview of the Igbos, Obioma is his narrative ensures to tinsel the narrative with instances that implicate the assertion on the role as well as limitation of Chi. Obioma projects the Igbo philosophy as Solomon's Chi mentions:

I stepped out of the body of my host while he was conscious. I did this because I see myself as his representative in the realm of the spirits. I stand within my host and gaze at every moment of his hands, every step of his feet, every motion of his body. To me, the body of my host is a screen on which the entirety of his life is displayed. For while in a host I'm nothing but an empty vessel filled by the life of a man, rendered concrete by that life. It is thus from the place of witness that I observe him live, and his life becomes my testimony. Yet a Chi is constrained while in the body of its host. While there, it becomes nearly impossible to see or hear what is present or spoken in the supernatural realm. But when one exit one's host, one becomes privy to things beyond the realm of man (31).

The foregoing rendition recognizes that as much as the Igbo World view holds that the guardian spirit has its strength, it also dictates that it's weakness is also present. For example, despite its attribute as a spirit, Solomon's Chi admits that "[...] a guardian spirit cannot see the future and thus cannot fully know what it's hosts will do"(16). Again, the Chi uncovers that men must be left to be independent, therefore if by virtue of experience a particular chi may not be able to divine the possible outcome of a phenomenon, it may not be able to do much in interfering in the activity of the host. The chi notes in, "as the guardian spirit the same scenario," I could sense it. But because you caution us, guardian spirits, nor to interfere in every affair of our hosts, to allow man to execute his will and be man, I sought not to stop

him,"(19). To put it in its exactitude, the Chi is as blind to deciphering the future as the host. However, there are cases where it's strength is projected, especially when it comes in contact with another spiritual entity that is a threat to its host life as seen in the instant where it's host, Solomon but have to contend with Solomon's Chi prove to be an impasse.

The argument has so far implied that the Igbos believe in the spiritual world which coexist with the physical world yet exists both independently. The very presence of the spiritual world as an inexorably concrete belief in different spirit-inhabitant domiciled in varied spiritual realm. To capture the Igbo World view regarding the reincarnation, Obioma suggests that the Chi is a spirit that is in a constant cycle of life - a fusion of life in the world of the living and life in the world of the living dead. In this understanding of the cosmology, the return of the Chi to the spirit world is considered to be a temporary linger before an arrangement is created for the Chi to be assigned to its new host. In essence, this suggest an endless circle of movement. Speaking of the rare moment of the first experience of the chi on earth and the level of bewilderment that comes with this foremost contact, the testifier confesses scends with the reincarnating body of the new host towards the land, what reveals itself to the eye astonishes" (13; my emphasis). This significantly projects the first understanding that the Igbo people, given their belief in the concrete existence of the spiritual, equally believe that is created for the possibility of reincarnation. Therefore, it is couched in the worldview of the people that life is cyclical.

To emphasize the phenomenon of reincarnation as part of the people's world view, Obioma creatively uses his main character, the Chi of Solomon, to substantiate this rendition in various instances. In its account, it speaks of its earlier host, Ejinkeonye Isigadi as demonstrating a trait now evident in its present hosts. Not only was this host mentioned, but the Chi also tells the reader of its host in the last cycle. It says, "In my last cycle, I guided an extraordinary, gifted man who read books and wrote stories, Ezike Nkeonye, who was the older brother of the mother of my present host"(62). Again, elsewhere in its account, the Chi hints on its former host Yagazie. In a rare moment of introspective comparison in the course of the narrative account, the Chi relays, "there were chandeliers and mantle pieces, articles I had seen in homes when my former host Yagazie was in Virginia, in the land of the brutal white man"(116). All of these pieces of testimony resolutely iterate the belief system that characterizes the world view of the people. It clairvoyantly confirms that there is an abode beyond the physical which is the spiritual and that "the separation between the world of mankind and the spirit is only leaf - thin", Yet they co-exist. It then follows, guided intuitively, that there are elements that inhabit the unseen realm, one of which is the guardian spirit among seven other spirit element inhabitants.

The Igbo World view may not be perfect in terms of the constitutive parts that make up the whole but one of the things that it identify with is it's effort in maintaining order and equity. In ensuring the attainment of this ambition, the structure of hierarchy, principles of order and complementary is well weaved in the worldview of the people. In line with the Igbo philosophy, the structure of complementarity is a constant marker in the being of the people. Every element or aspect of life is complemented by another aspect to create a balance; even then, this is not realized chaotically, rather there is a construction of hierarchy and power relations. To foreground this, the Igbo people believe that the complementary alternative to male is female, therefore, the female is not subordinated to the male but complements the male in terms of social duties, however, in the familial construction, the male is lord to the female. All of these measures are well-defined on the worldview of the Igbos in order to eschew any emergence of chaos. In the concretization of this, Obioma ostensibly indicate that the heavens and all its associative elements are male while the earth and its characteristic features are female. It is upon the knowledge of his people's worldview that he relays this in his text. In the infrastructural establishment of balance, the heavens is complemented by earth and while the former is defined with a sex, the other also is identified with another.

The bulk of the argument here takes a position that Chigozie Obioma's text, *An Orchestra of Minorities* provides a conscionable mind with an analytical pathway and insight through which the worldview of the Igbo people can be appreciated. Congenital to the text is the spiritual essence and construction couched in the worldview of the people. As demonstrated in the text, almost every phenomenon has a spiritual implication that explains it or validates it.

Conclusion

By examining the primary text, it becomes evident that Obioma adeptly conveys the complexities of the Igbo worldview and its transformation in the face of external influences. The author skillfully captures the depth and richness of Igbo cultural practices, beliefs, and values, in highlighting their significance in shaping individual and collective identities. Moreover, the novel illustrates the repercussions of colonialism and the encroachment of Western ideologies on traditional Igbo society, leading to the erosion of cultural heritage and the destabilization of established social structures.

Remarkably, *An Orchestra of Minorities* offers valuable insights into the Igbo worldview from different perspectives and time periods. These novels serve as powerful literary representations that deepen our understanding of the Igbo culture and its resilience in the face of external forces. They remind us of the importance of cultural preservation, the need to appreciate diverse worldviews, and the profound impact that societal changes can have on individuals and communities.

Through the exploration of these literary works, readers are invited to contemplate the significance of cultural heritage, the complexities of cultural encounters, and the enduring spirit of the Igbo people.

Chigozie Obioma's *An Orchestra of Minorities* provides unique insights into the Igbo worldview. The novel offers a contemporary exploration of the Igbo worldview and cosmology. The novel delves into Igbo cosmology, highlighting the interconnectedness of the physical and spiritual realms. Obioma portrays the significance of spirits, the principle of reincarnation, and the role of the chi in mediating between the physical and spiritual worlds. Through the protagonist Chinonso's journey and encounters, Obioma weaves a rich tapestry that incorporates Igbo beliefs and perspectives, capturing the essence of the Igbo worldview in a modern context.

An Orchestra of Minorities presents a contemporary and philosophical exploration. The constant retrospective yearnings seem to suggest that the progressive advancement of age engenders worrisome implications. For example, Obioma recognizes that changes is inevitable and, in many ways, progressive but he also points out following his narrative as he continually retrospect in a comparative manner the pristine order associated with the past that is now uncharitable perforated, so that the fabric of traditional existence is defaced with alien aspirations. The narrator in his text mentions in an episode,

Agujiegbe, this buying and selling of water has always amazed me. The old fathers would have imagined, even in the time of drought, that water-the most abundant provision of the great earth goddess herself-could be sold [...](Obioma 88).

Elsewhere the narrator carries out a comparative analysis noting “but let’s look at the times of the wise fathers, how indispensable the great mothers here [...] they were like the Chi of the society. They restored order and equilibrium when order became broken” (Obioma 65). These textual indicators, although, implies that there is a transition from the traditional society to a modern one which may be good, especially in the area of an industrial ambulation. However, as noticed in the first remark, this industrial progression is marked off by capitalism that is averse to the traditional philosophy of communalism. The second statement implies a complete derailment.

Undoubtedly, the text serves to remind us of the rich cultural value of the Igbos, establishing why such cultural values should be preserved. It educates not just the Igbo readers but every person whose root can be traced to an equally rich culture of the dangers in superimposing an alien culture on one’s culture which can lead to an erosion of self. As the text seeks to bare different aspects of the worldview of the Igbo people, it also endears the Igbo reader to appreciate the gradually extincting worldview. Through oral elements such as proverbs, mythological

accounts, cultural displays common saying and idiomatic expressions, folklores, taboos, invocations of cosmological exposition, as well as philosophy, the Igbo worldview as reflected in the texts is projected. The significance of all these aid identity preservation, and socio-cultural understanding/education. Encouraging the understanding of traditional values secreted within the pot-pourri of worldview will help in the realization of a functional society because it is true that such cultural understanding fosters morality. It then follows that government should be forthright in legislating policies and build structures that can aid the preservation of this. In addition, cultural education can be incorporated into the school's curriculum not just language alone as we see today.

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